

Title: Level and Factors Associated with Adherence to Anti Retro Viral Drugs among Patients Attending the Anti Retro Viral Therapy (Art) Clinic of a Tertiary Center in South East Nigeria.

Running Title: Adherence to Antiretroviral Therapy in South-East Nigeria

Ofonakara Uzochukwu^{1,2,3}, Ohanme Eugene Ohams², Ntaji Maureen Iru⁴, Elom Peter¹, Nwosu Ngozi³, Orofuke Grace Ngozi⁵, Ebulum Genevieve Chimaoge¹, Onwe Francis Idenyi¹, Nweke Chibueze Ogbodo⁶

¹Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Clinical Medicine, David Umahi Federal University Teaching Hospital, Uburu, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

²Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, Faculty of Basic Clinical Medicine, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu-Alike, Ikwo, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

³National Primary Health Care agency, Abuja, Nigeria

⁴Department of Community Medicine Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State Nigeria

⁵Delta State Primary Health Care Development Agency, Asaba, Delta State

⁶Department of Family Medicine, Faculty of Clinical Medicine, Alex Ekwueme Federal Teaching Hospital, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

Corresponding author: Ass Prof Ofonakara Uzochukwu

Abstract

Background: Optimal adherence to antiretroviral therapy (ART) is essential for viral suppression, prevention of drug resistance, and improved quality of life among people living with HIV (PLHIV). However, maintaining recommended adherence levels remains challenging in resource-limited settings such as Nigeria, underscoring the need to identify adherence patterns and influencing factors to inform effective, evidence-based interventions. **Method:** A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted among PLHIV attending the antiretroviral therapy clinic of a tertiary health facility in Enugu, South-East Nigeria. Adult HIV-positive patients aged 18 years and above who had been on ART for at least one month were recruited. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics and logistic regression to determine factors associated with non-adherence. **Results:** Among the 452 respondents, only

37.6% achieved optimal adherence (>95%), with a mean adherence score of 90.21 ± 13.89 . About 22.8% missed at least one dose in the two weeks preceding the study, while 53.8% did not consistently follow dosage instructions. Commonly reported reasons for non-adherence included being busy with other activities, forgetting to take medications, and being away from home. Higher adherence levels were observed among participants aged 31–40 years, those with tertiary education, and urban residents. Alcohol use, smokeless tobacco use, and mobility-related factors were significant predictors of non-adherence ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** Optimal adherence to ART among the participants was low. Substance use and mobility-related factors significantly influenced non-adherence, underscoring the need for targeted, context-specific adherence-enhancing interventions for PLHIV.

Keywords: Adherence, antiretroviral therapy, factors associated

Introduction

In 2020, approximately 1.5 million [1.0 million–2.0 million] individuals acquired new HIV infections. Additionally, 680,000 [480,000–1.0 million] people died from AIDS-related conditions in 2020, which is slightly lower than the 690,000 deaths reported in 2019, and significantly lower than 1.1 million in 2010 and 2 million [1.7 million–2.3 million] in 2005. Since the onset of the epidemic, 79.3 million [55.9 million–110 million] individuals have contracted HIV, while 36.3 million [27.2 million–47.8 million] have died from AIDS-related causes.¹

According to the fact sheet, by 30 June 2021, 28.2 million people were receiving antiretroviral therapy (ART), compared to 7.8 million [6.9 million–7.9 million] in 2010. In 2020, 73% [56–88%] of all individuals living with HIV were on treatment; treatment coverage included 74% [57–90%] of adults aged 15 and above, and 54% [37–69%] of children aged 0–14. The data further revealed that 79% [61–95%] of adult females aged 15 and older were receiving treatment, compared to 68% [52–83%] of their male counterparts.²

In Nigeria, HIV/AIDS remains a significant public health concern. The country holds the second-highest burden of the disease globally, with 3.2 million people living with HIV, second only to South Africa, which has 6.8 million cases³. The National AIDS Reproductive Health Survey (NARHS) of 2012 reported a national prevalence of 3.4%, reflecting a slight decline from the 3.6% estimated in 2007. Prevalence in 2012 peaked among individuals aged 35 to 39 years (4.4%), and was lowest in the 15–19 age group (2.9%). Among males aged 35 to 39, prevalence was highest at 5.3%, while it stood at 4.2% among females aged 30 to 34 years⁴.

Although access to ART is essential, patient adherence to treatment regimens is equally critical. Sustained adherence levels of over 90–95% are needed for long-term viral suppression and to delay disease progression to AIDS⁵. Non-adherence to ART is a prominent and adjustable factor contributing to disease advancement in people living with HIV (PLHIV)⁶. Thus, monitoring patient adherence is fundamental to effective HIV care, management, and research.

While several other factors such as genetic variations in drug metabolism, initial immune suppression, existing drug resistance, and co-occurring opportunistic infections can impact ART success, adherence remains one of the most modifiable determinants of treatment outcomes⁷. Adherence barriers are widespread among PLHIV; however, some evidence suggests viral suppression can still occur with 95% adherence, depending on the treatment regimen, follow-up period, and adherence measurement methods⁸. Ensuring adherence to ART continues to be a pressing public health issue globally, as optimal clinical and virologic outcomes heavily depend on adherence. Conversely, poor adherence can quickly lead to drug resistance, narrowing treatment options, increasing healthcare costs, and accelerating disease progression⁹.

This study aims to assess the level of adherence to ART and identify associated factors among PLHIV attending a tertiary hospital clinic in southeastern Nigeria¹⁰.

Study Area

The study was conducted at a tertiary healthcare facility located in the southeastern region of Nigeria. Eligible participants included HIV-positive adults aged 18 years and above who had been on ART for a minimum of one month prior to data collection.

Study Participants

A cross-sectional study design was used, involving adult male and female patients who regularly attended the ART clinic at the tertiary center.

Study Design

The study targeted adult male and female patients, aged 18 years and older, who were registered and receiving ART at the designated clinic.

Sample Size Determination and Sampling

The required sample size was calculated using the Cochran formula:

$$N = (Z^2PQ / D^2)^{11}$$

Where:

- **P** = proportion of people with good baseline adherence (89.5%) from a prior study in Enugu (8)
- **Q** = 1 – P = 0.105
- **Z** = 1.96 (for 95% confidence level)
- **D** = 0.05 (precision level)

$$N = (1.96^2 \times 0.895 \times 0.105) / 0.0025 = 144$$

After adjusting for a 20% non-response rate:

$$\text{Adjusted N} = 144 / 0.80 = 180$$

Nevertheless, 452 eligible participants were available and all were enrolled in the study.

Data Collection Methods

Data were gathered using a pre-tested, interviewer-administered anonymous questionnaire focused on patient adherence to ART. Collected data included socio-demographic profiles, adherence behaviors, and related factors. Each questionnaire was reviewed daily for completeness and consistency, and securely stored to protect participant confidentiality. The investigator checked for any missing or illogical responses and corrected them as needed.

Data Analysis

Independent variables comprised socio-demographic information (age, gender, marital status, education, occupation, religion, etc.), assessed via the structured questionnaire. Dependent variables included adherence level and CD4 count.

Outcome Variables

Adherence was determined based on self-reported pill intake over the preceding seven days and pill count. The formula used for adherence calculation was:

$$\text{Adherence (\%)} = (\text{Number of doses taken} / \text{Number of doses prescribed}) \times 100 \quad (54)$$

A dose refers to the amount of medication taken at a given time, which could be a single dose, daily dose, or total dose over the treatment course. An adherence level of 95% or higher was categorized as “good adherence.”

Data entry and analysis were performed using IBM SPSS version 25. Quantitative variables were summarized using means and standard deviations, while frequencies and proportions were used for qualitative data. Chi-square tests assessed associations between adherence and categorical variables, while multiple logistic regression identified independent predictors of adherence. Results were reported using odds ratios and 95% confidence intervals, with a significance level set at 5%.

Ethical Approval

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of the University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital, ItukuOzalla, Enugu.

Results

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants

Variables	(n=452)%
Age (years)	
18-30	62(13.7)
31-40	160(35.4)
41-50	153(33.8)
51-60	60(13.3)
>60	17(3.7)
Mean \pm SD	41.72 \pm 10.16
Gender	
Male	133(29.4)
Female	319(70.6)
Education	
None	17(3.7)
Primary	83(18.4)
Secondary	204(45.1)
Tertiary	148(32.7)
Marital Status	
Never married	99(21.9)
Currently Married	236(52.2)
Separated	13(2.9)
Divorced	15(3.3)
Widowed	89(19.7)
Currently employed	
Yes	226(50.0)
No	226(50.0)
Place of residence	
Rural	249(55.1)
Urban	203(44.9)
Distance from place of residence to treatment clinic	
Less than 5 mins	8(1.8)
6-30 mins	70(15.5)
31mins - 1 hour	153(33.8)
More than an hour	221(48.9)

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants. The mean age of the participants was 41.72 ± 10.16 , 133(29.4) were males, 319(70.6) were females. Also, 99(21.9) were never married, 236(52.2) were currently married, 249(55.1) live in rural area while 203(44.9) live in urban area.

Table 2: Social habits of the participants dis-aggregated into intervention and control groups

Variables	
Ever used alcohol	(n=452)
Yes	233(51.5)
No	219(48.5)
Currently uses alcohol	n=233
Yes	103(44.2)
No	130(55.8)
How often respondent takes alcohol	n=103
Daily	5(4.9)
Weekly	11(10.7)
Occasionally	87(84.5)
Ever used smokeless tobacco products	n=452
Yes	25(5.6)
No	427(94.5)
Respondent who currently uses smokeless tobacco products	n=25
Yes	6(24.0)
No	19(76.0)
How often respondent use smokeless tobacco	n=6
Weekly	3(50.0)
Occasionally	3(50.0)
Ever used smoked tobacco	n=452
Yes	21(4.6)
No	431(95.4)
current use of smoked tobacco	n=21
Yes	5(23.8)

No	16(76.2)
How often respondent smoke tobacco	n=5
Daily	2(40.0)
Weekly	1(20.0)
Occasionally	2(40.0)

Table 2 shows the social habits of the participants. Current use of alcohol was 103(44.2%). For smokeless tobacco, 6(24.0%) currently use it while only 5(23.8%) currently used smoked tobacco.

Table 3: Proportion of participants with good baseline adherence

Variable	(n=452)%
Adherence	
Good	170(37.6)
Poor	282(62.4)

The table above, showed that the proportion of participants with adherence >95% was 37.6%.

Table4: Mean score of adherence of the participants

Variable		(n=452)
Adherence		90.21±13.89

* Mean scores of adherence was calculated by summing the adherence scores and dividing by the number of participants.

The table showed that mean adherence score of the 452 respondents was 90.21±13.89.

Table 5: The number of times patients missed doses

Variable	(n=452)
Doses missed in the last 2 weeks	
None	349(77.2)
1-3	90(19.9)
>3	13(2.9)
How often they follow specific dosage times and instructions	
Never	30(6.6)
Some of the time	70(15.5)
Most of the time	143(31.6)
All the time	209(46.2)

Table 5 above showed that a large number of participants 103(22.8%) missed their drug for at least once in the last 2 weeks and a greater percentage of respondents 243(53.8%) do not follow specific dosage instructions all the time.

Table 6: Factors associated with adherence

Variable	(n=452)
Felt sick or ill	
Yes	16(3.5)
No	436(96.5)
Felt depressed/unhappy / overwhelmed	
Yes	26(5.8)
No	426(94.2)
Ran out of pills	
Yes	8(1.8)
No	444(98.2)
Felt good (didn't need to take drugs)	
Yes	25(5.5)
No	427(94.5)

The table shows that the reasons for missing of drugs by the respondents; 16(3.5%) were ill, 26(5.8%) were depressed or unhappy, 8(1.8%) ran out of pills while 25(5.5%) felt good and did not take their drugs.

Table 6: factors associated with adherence

Variable	(n=452)
Were away from home	
Yes	354(78.3)
No	98(21.7)
Were busy with other things	
Yes	383(84.7)
No	69(15.3)
Simply forgot	
Yes	356(78.8%)
No	96(21.2%)
Had too many pills to take	
Yes	18(4.0%)
No	434(96.0%)
Feel frequency of dose is cumbersome	
Yes	13(2.9%)
No	439(97.1%)
Wanted to avoid side effects	
Yes	31(6.9)
No	421(93.1)
Did not want others to notice you taking medication	
Yes	37(8.2%)
No	415(91.8%)
Fell asleep/ Slept through dose time	
Yes	38(8.4%)
No	414(91.6%)
Felt like the drug was toxic/harmful	
Yes	25(5.5)
No	427(94.5)

The table above shows that the commonest reason associated with non-adherence was; busy with other things 383(84.7%) followed by simply forgot 356(78.8%) and were away from home 354(78.3%)

Table 7: Relationship between socio demographic characteristics and Adherence

FACTORS

Variable	Adherence		Total (n=452)	X ² / pvalue
	Poor (n=282))%	Good (n=170))%		
Age (years)				
<=20	6(85.7)	1(14.3)	7	5.555/ 0.475
21-30	35(63.6)	20(36.4)	55	
31-40	92(57.5)	68(42.5)	160	
41-50	101(66.0)	52(34.0)	153	
51-60	37(61.7)	23(38.3)	60	
61-70	9(69.2)	4(30.8)	13	
71-80	2(50.0)	2(50.0)	4	
Gender				
Male	82(61.7)	51(38.3)	133	0.047 / 0.828
Female	200(62.7)	119(37.3)	319	
Education				
None	15(88.2)	2(11.8)	17	8.765/ 0.033
Primary	53(63.9)	30(36.1)	83	
Secondary	136(66.7)	68(33.3)	204	
Tertiary	78(52.7)	70(47.3)	148	
Marital Status				
Never married	64(64.6)	35(35.4)	99	2.949 / 0.566

Currently Married	143(60.6)	93(39.4)	236	
Separated	10(76.9)	3(23.1)	13	
Divorced	9(60.0)	6(40)	15	
Widowed	56(62.9)	33(37.1)	89	
Currently employed				
Yes	134(59.3)	92(40.7)	226	2.672 / 0.102
No	148(65.5)	78(34.5)	226	
Place of residence				
Rural	139(63.2)	81(36.8)	220	1.181 / 0.277
Urban	143(61.6)	89(38.4)	232	
Distance from place of residence to treatment clinic				
Less than 5 mins	7(87.5)	1(12.5)	8	2.736 / 0.434
6-30 mins	47(67.1)	23(32.9)	70	
31mins - 1 hour	88(57.5)	65(42.5)	153	
More than an hour	140(63.3)	81(36.7)	221	

The table above shows that the highest proportion of participants with good adherence were among 31-40 with 68(42.5%), tertiary education 70 (47.3) and urban residents 89 (38.4). Those who had no basic education $p > 0.033$ are less likely to be adherent than others.

Table 8: Relationship between Social habits and Adherence

Variable	Intervention Poor (n=282)	Good (n=170)	Total (n=452)	X ² / pvalue
Ever used alcohol				
Yes	152(65.2)	81(34.8)	233	9.938/0.002
No	130(59.4)	89(40.6)	219	
Currently use alcohol			n=233	
Yes	79(76.7)	24(23.3)	103	54.279/ 0.001
No	53(40.8)	77(59.2)	130	

Have you ever used smokeless tobacco products			n=452	
Yes	15(60.0)	10(40.0)	25	0.001 / 0.988
No	267(62.5)	160(37.5)	427	
If yes do you currently use smokeless tobacco products			n=25	
Yes	6(100.0)	0(0.0)	6	5.000 / 0.044
No	9(47.4)	10(62.6)	19	
Ever used smoked tobacco	n=452			
Yes	11(52.4)	10(47.6)	21	0.904 / 0.342
No	271(62.9)	160(37.1)	431	
Do you currently use smoked tobacco			n=21	
Yes	4(80.0)	1(20.0)	5	7.000 / 0.008
No	7(43.8)	9(56.3)	16	

The table above shows that proportion of participants were more adherent were among those who currently use no alcohol 77(59.2), do not currently use smokeless 10(62.6) and those who do not use smoked tobacco. Those who had ever used alcohol $p > 0.022$ are less likely to be adherent than others.

VARIABLE	Pvalue	Odd ratio	95% confidence interval	
Education				
None*	0.071	1		
Primary	0.074	7.288	0.827	64.209
Secondary	0.187	0.574	0.252	1.309
Tertiary	0.154	0.643	0.351	1.179
Ever used alcohol				
Yes *		1		
No	0.027	1.865	1.073	3.244
If yes do you currently use smokeless tobacco products				
Yes		1		
No	0.021	2.500	1.17	5.34
Away from home				
Yes		1		
No	0.041	0.430	0.191	0.965

*Reference value

The table shows that ever use of alcohol $p < 0.027$, current use of smokeless tobacco $p < 0.021$ and being away from home $p < 0.041$ were significantly associated with non-adherence.

Discussion

The average adherence score in this study was 90.21 ± 13.89 , which closely aligns with the 92.6% adherence rate reported in a study conducted at a tertiary hospital in Ilorin¹². Similarly, the result compares well with the 89.5% adherence rate recorded across eight comprehensive healthcare facilities in Enugu¹³. However, this study's mean adherence was notably higher than that observed in the Upper West Region of Ghana, which reported a lifetime adherence rate of 62.2%, as well as the 61% recorded in Belgium. In contrast, the adherence score in this study was lower than that reported in NnamdiAzikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi, which found an adherence rate of 97.8%. It was also lower than the self-reported adherence rates from four national surveys in Kenya, Rwanda, Uganda, and Ethiopia, which were 96.6%, 96.7%, 100%, and 96.6% respectively¹⁴.

Numerous studies have highlighted the challenges of baseline adherence within ART programs. In this study, a significant number of participants; 103 (22.8%) reported missing at least one dose of their medication in the past two weeks, and over half; 243 (53.8%) acknowledged not consistently following the prescribed dosage instructions. This contrasts with findings from a study in the United States where, among 75 patients across ten AACTG sites, only 11% missed a dose the day before the interview, and 17% within the two days prior¹⁵.

Personal reasons cited by respondents for missed doses included being ill (3.5%), feeling depressed or unhappy (5.8%), running out of medication (1.8%), or feeling well enough to skip doses (5.5%). These reasons are consistent with findings reported by Maduka et al. (2011). Dose omission is a key contributor to poor adherence¹⁶. According to Wise et al., non-adherence undermines ART efficacy and increases the risk of drug resistance and virologic failure¹⁷.

The most frequently reported reasons for non-adherence in this study were being occupied with other tasks (84.7%), forgetfulness (78.8%), and being away from home (78.3%). These results correspond with a study in Ghana which identified forgetfulness (46.1%) and lack of food (7.3%) as primary reasons for missed doses¹⁸, as well as findings in Cameroon by Mbuagbaw et al. (2017) where forgetfulness was the leading factor¹⁹. Forgetfulness may be the endpoint of multiple underlying causes such as being busy or away from home highlighting the need for targeted interventions²⁰. Peng et al (2020) emphasized the potential of mobile phones as effective, low-cost tools to support adherence due to their widespread use and adaptability in delivering reminders and health communication²¹.

This study also examined how socio-demographic factors influenced adherence. Participants aged 31–40 years had the highest adherence (42.5%), followed by those with tertiary education (47.3%), and urban residents (38.4%). Individuals without formal education ($p > 0.033$) were less likely to be adherent. Higher adherence rates were also observed among participants who reported not consuming alcohol (59.2%), not using smokeless tobacco (62.6%), and not smoking tobacco (56.3%). Participants with a history of alcohol use ($p > 0.022$) showed reduced adherence.

These observations were supported by logistic regression, which identified ever consuming alcohol ($p < 0.027$), current use of smokeless tobacco ($p < 0.021$), and being away from home ($p < 0.041$) as significant predictors of non-adherence.

The findings are consistent with those from a study in Enugu, which indicated that factors like adequate knowledge, HIV status disclosure, absence of co-morbidities, and avoidance of substance abuse are linked with better adherence²². Similarly, research among adults on ART in eight comprehensive health facilities in Enugu revealed that being on ART for over five years, abstaining from alcohol, and avoiding traditional remedies are linked with higher adherence¹³. These patterns are also in agreement with a study in Ghana, which identified forgetfulness as the top reason for missed doses²³, and a study in Cameroon where higher education levels were statistically significant predictors of adherence above 95%²⁴.

Conclusion

This study found a relatively low proportion of participants with good baseline adherence to ART. Key factors associated with poor adherence included ever consuming alcohol ($p < 0.027$), current use of smokeless tobacco ($p < 0.021$), and being away from home ($p < 0.041$).

Declarations

Acknowledgements

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Ethics approval and consent to participate

Ethical clearance for this study was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of David Umahi Federal University Health Sciences Teaching Hospital Uburu, Ebonyi State, Nigeria (DUFUHSTH/02/Vol.4/038). Written informed consent was obtained and confidentiality ensured.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they do not have any conflicts of interest.

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Authors' contributions

Conception and design: Ofonakara Uzochukwu, Ohanme Eugene Ohams, Elom Peter, Nwosu Ngozi. **Collection and assembly of data:** Orofuoke Grace Ngozi, Ebulum Genevieve Chimaoge, Onwe Francis Idenyi. **Analysis and interpretation of the data:** Onwe Francis Idenyi, Nweke Chibueze Ogbodo. **Drafting of the article:** Ofonakara Uzochukwu, Ohanme Eugene Ohams. **Critical revision of the article for important intellectual content:** Ofonakara Uzochukwu, Ohanme Eugene Ohams, Orofuoke Grace Ngozi, Elom Peter . **Statistical expertise:** Ofonakara Uzochukwu, Nwosu Ngozi. **Final approval and guarantor of the article:** Ebulum Genevieve Chimaoge

Availability of data and materials

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request (druzochukwu@yahoo.com)

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